

TOURISM IN HEALTH PROMOTION – A STRATEGY IN STRESS MANAGEMENT AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT OF UNIVERSITY ACADEMIC STAFF

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Abstract:

Despite the growth of leisure travel and stress coping research based analysis of leisure and tourism, stress coping have been performed rarely. The purpose of the present study is to examine how University staffs cope with stress through participation in leisure and tourism activities, and how work related stress affect their organizational commitment using data collected from a focus group interview approach and a self-developed questionnaire consisting of 25 items design to elicit information about the range of methods university staff used seeking information about leisure, tourism and how to cope with stress and the contribution leisure and tourism intervention to this process, it will further inquire about social, work environment, the frequency and type of leisure tourism activity, health conditions and organizational commitment and work stress coping mechanism. For this purpose the study 45 randomly selected academic staff from all the departments in the faculty of education, in Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria Nigeria was surged to establish the correlation between academic staff leisure and tourism activity and their characteristic life style of their living environment as well as their working conditions the subject were aged between 30-70yrs while their average age was 35 their job included teaching, research, supervision of students project, marking and compiling exams records etc..

Keywords: tourism, stress, organization, commitment, health & promotion

Introduction

Globally, the evolution of stress is attached to work, and work pressure. Work-related stress is at alarming stage now in this generation everything is moving at a very high pace. This speedy pace of things these days made work more stressful thereby exerting unbearable pressures on health especially academics in higher education. This result to health problems like high blood pressure, poor mental articulation or co-ordination, gastrointestinal problems, eye malfunctioning, work-related stress as it is affecting workers` health. In Nigeria, death particularly premature ones are common among academics staff and are at the peak. According to Benjamin (2003) death rate is presumed to be depending because of health implications of work-related stress among workers in the country, particularly those in the academic. Going by the lecturer-students ratio, it is observed that most of Universities in Nigeria are absolutely flooded. For example, Arubayi (2009) stated that lecturer student`s ratio varies from one discipline to another at the University level. Disciplines such as medicine and engineering are expected to have a ratio 1:9 as recommended, for the science, 1:12; the social sciences 1:20 and education and humanities 1:23, these recommendations are not observe in Nigeria Universities.

This study aimed at establishing a correlation between life style and physical work of University staff and how leisure and tourism activities can serve as an intervention strategy in stress management and improve organizational commitment. The study will also establish the relationship between leisure and tourism and frequency of health problems and active engagement in leisure and tourism activities. The study is set to answer the following questions: Leisure activities influence stress management and organizational commitment their by improve health promotion and education of University staffs; tourism activities influence stress management and organizational commitment and their by improving health promotion and education of University staffs.

Statement of the Problem

Tourism has been used as in other field as Gilbert, (1999) pointed out that even this simple term has deferent meanings in the USA and Britain. In Great Britain, the word tourism covers all travel for whatever purpose, whereas in the USA it refers to leisure travel only. In this paper, the British use of the term will be adopted. The tourism industry covers what in the USA is variously referred to as the visitor industry, the hospitality industry, the travel industry or the convention and tourism industry,

Stremersh & Tellis (2002), defined Tourism as a phenomena and relationship arising from the travel and stay of non-residents in so far as they do not lead to permanent residence and are not connected with any earning. The world Tourism organization definition of a tourist is someone who moves away from home on a temporary or short-term basis for at least 24 hours, whether travelling in his or her own country (domestic tourism) or going to another country (international tourism). The term leisure travel clearly applies to what people do in their spare free on non-working hours, but once again this can cover several purposes. It applies to what people do on holiday, even if it is only a day's holiday. This holiday travel may also refer to as pleasure tourism. The term leisure travel may also be used for visit to friends and relatives, and conducting personal business. The pleasure tourist is attracted to cities because of their historic buildings, interesting urban landscapes, art galleries, theatres, sports events and other entertainment. The various types of Tourism for recreation and leisure that people take in for their betterment include:

- i. Eco Tourism: this has to do with based tourism, including National parks, Game Reserves, Sanctuaries and Wetlands.
- ii. Heritage/Cultural Tourism: Various forms of tourism are found in Nigeria; culture assets, especially the festivals, are amongst the most fascinating the world over.
- iii. Sport tourism: Nigerians are sports lovers and many have excelled in various sporting activities like soccer, athletes, golf, professional and traditional standard are scattered all over the country.
- iv. Conference/Business Tourism: Nigeria has emerged as one of African's centres for business and conferences in cities like Abuja, Kaduna and Port-Harcourt.
- v. Beach Tourism: Nigeria has over 700km of coastline, covered with unpolluted sandy beaches, ready for investment. Prominent area and sites are Lagos Encravos, Port-Harcourt, Benny and Ibeno beaches among others.
- vi. Adventure Safari: this has to do with mountains or plateau experience, rocks climbing, trekking etc. a very good instance is that of Wase Rock in Plateau State, Zuma Rock in Niger State, Olimo Rock in Ogun State the three (3) Sister Rock in Adamawa State, Gwaza Hills Borno State, etc.
- vii. Rural Tourism: These are types of tourism that have to do with village life-styles, farm, houses, ranches and plantations, hunting historic districts, gardens etc. various 'tourist' villages are now found in Nigeria, I.e; Abuja tourist Village etc.

Several studies have shown have given considerable attention to the relationship between job stress and organizational commitment, that work-related stress is a product of lack of participation in physical activities in the form of leisure and tourism activities in a study conducted by Viljoen and Rothman, 2009; Tarafdar, 2011; Yaghobi *et al.*'s (2009) found out that stress negatively influence organizational commitment, higher work stress has negative effect on organizational commitment and that the impact of techno-stress among professionals are reduced commitment towards organizational goals and values. As a result, employees may not be able to function well and will become a costly burden to their organizations. Kofoworola & Alayode (2012) looked at this situation from a different point of view. They believed that stress is actually a result of too much commitment in the work such as working overtime on several task simultaneously. Thus, they suggested that employees prioritize their work to alleviate stress. Work value vary from one employee to another, while some place emphasis on professional competence; others especially in the third world countries such as Nigeria are pre-occupied by the need for satisfaction of bread and butter. In any work setting, the higher the work values congruence of individual employee and his/her employment, the higher his job satisfaction, commitment and productivity. Leisure and tourism provides several means through which an individual can release tension of being stressed at work.

Some of these outlets include indulging in eco-tourism; visiting games parks, sanctuaries or wetland which are available in Yankari games reserve, Sport tourism; Heritage or Cultural tourism; rural tourism; village lifestyle, ranches and plantations, garden and other natural centres. It is with this in mind that the study will adopt and use Chatman's Theory of normative behaviour (2000) to understand the processes that surround information seeking on leisure and tourism activities in health promotion and education as an intervention strategy in stress management and organizational commitment of academic staff of Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria. Information seeking behaviour shows that information seeking has generally been accepted as dynamic and non-linear (Foster, 2005; Kuhlthau 2006). People experience the information search process as interplay of thoughts, feelings and actions (Kuhlthau 2006; Donald 2007). Information seeking has been found to be linked to variety interpersonal communication behaviours beyond question-asking, to include strategies such as candidate answer. Robinson's (2011) illustrate how research suggests that when seeking information at work, people; rely on both other people and information repositories (e.g. documents and databases), and spend similar amounts of time consulting each 7.8% and 6.4% work time, respectively; 14.2% in depending on the description of time among the constituent information seeking stages differs depending

on the source. When consulting other people, people spend less time locating the information source and information within that source, similar time understanding the information, and more time problem solving and decision making, than when consulting information repositories. Furthermore, the research found that people spend substantially more time receiving information passively (i.e., information that they have not requested) than actively (i.e., information that they have requested), and this pattern is also reflected when they provide others with information.

Wilson (2000) described information behaviour as the totality of human behaviour in relation to sources and channels of information, including both active and passive information-seeking, and information use. He described information seeking behaviour as purposive seeking of information as a consequence of a need to satisfy some goal. Information seeking behaviour is the micro-level of behaviour employed by the system, or the pure method of creating and following up on a search. Sinha (2011) described tourism information as that enables a potential tourist to access the destination of interest. It is any literatures or published materials that enable a tourist to have insight information about attractions and destinations, various practices of the local people in the destination, taxes and tipping, postal services, shop hours and restaurants. He further state that, source of information on tourism are pamphlets, leaflets, journals, Newspaper, geographical and tourism maps, monographs images, audio recordings, Bulletins, brochures, flyers, travel guides, internets, television and documentaries, Radio and other bits of information materials on attractions of the areas to be visited, with some travel checklist including videos and web sites. However, tourism information itself is that information on areas of tourism that an individual is interested on. Kurent (2011) asserts that tourism information can be sought from internet, in the Library, video, friend and colleagues, documentaries from television (e.g) national, Geography wildlife, telephone call, travel guide such ad (the world heritage), national park news, bulletins, leaflets, flyers from hospitalities (e.g. hotels), tourism maps and signboards, newspapers, brochures, magazines, journals and directories.

Research Questions

1. *What are the health indicators of work related health stress and implications on academic staff?*
2. *What are the health implications differences of work-related stress between male and female academic staff?*

3. *What is the health implications of work-related stress associated with their positions (rank) on academic staff?*

Significance and Objectives of the Study

Tourism and leisure activities participation has long been established to have a number of health beneficial effects and also an important component in strategy designed to reduce health problems and promote life long active living, these research study will help in sensitizing university management in proving an enabling environment that will encourage staff to actively participate in leisure and plan their tourism activities for effective management of stress and thus obtain the opportunity to live healthier and become more productive in discharging their responsibilities, so also changing the negative attitudes of university staff. This study will create awareness and bring to the knowledge of university academic staff union that there is the need for them in negotiating or rejecting conditions of their service that are not favourable or will affect to their health status.

Literature Review

Tourism is the geography of consumption outside the home area; it is about how and why people travel to consume, whether it be historic buildings, landscapes, art and museum collections, or sports and entertainment. It is concerned with what makes tourist travel, what determines how far and in what direction they move. The term leisure travel clearly applies to what people do in their spare free on non-working hours, but once again this can cover several purposes. It applies to what people do on holiday, even if it is only a day's holiday. This holiday travel may also refer to as pleasure tourism. The term leisure travel may also be used for visit to friends and relatives, and conducting personal business. The pleasure tourist is attracted to cities because of their historic buildings, interesting urban landscapes, art galleries, theatres, sports events and other entertainment.

Work-related stress is common in organizational context of the global world today. Cater 2005; & Daniel 2008 submits that physical work and lifestyle result into mental and emotional stress their further reported that employees frequently experience stress that increase their risk of mental and physical health and thus affect their job performance. University staff works round the clock from Monday to Friday and sometimes, including weekends. Moreover, the weekend that is normally used as leisure has now been affected adversely with the introduction of part-time and

consultancy services leaving them with occasional Sundays which they use for worship or domestic chores; these give them no time to rest. Krippendorf (2010) opined that we work in order to go on holiday and we need the holidays in order to be able to work again. He stress that tourism is social therapy from the stress of the workaday routine. Therefore academics need time to rest from the workaday work of academic activities, hence the academics that intend to travel on annual leave outside the area of staying need information to decide options. Access to information is very important for human development, education, lives improvement, physical wellbeing and mental alertness. He further stress that access to information is the act of having information in whatever format that can be useful to an individual lives. Therefore, access to tourism information is a process of seeking and obtaining information that will lead a potential tourist to his/her destination. As a human being, we want to be informed, keep abreast of the latest event that affects, or are of interest to us. In the same vein, academics need information on leisure, recreation and tourism, they wants to know the latest football scores, a very legislation that affects their lives, economic activities that affects their daily living to be a part-taker.

The study of Ajala & Bolarinwa (2002) revealed that academic staff goes to work early and return home late throughout an academic session. This generally makes it difficult for them to undertake leisure and tourism activities. Tourism play important role in the economic, social, psychological, health and mentally wellbeing of a nation. It enhance academic stability and healthiness of an institution, it reduce the level of fatigue and stress and save us from stress related death as stress is one of the greatest course of many dead that occurred among academics. However, Egu, Ogbanna, Obike & Obiuto (2014) reported that the demand for education has become high; his results to over flooding in most of the Universities that leads to over population. Excessive work-overload is presumed to be an index lecturers` greatest stressor. Besides, there are others such as attending long hour meetings and meeting deadlines in submitting results and official reports such as reports on conduct of semester examination, project supervisions, frequent examination invigilation without intervals, Agbionu (2012) supported the assertion as they maintained that many lectures would agree that lecturing is not only a hard work, but can be full of stress. They added that pressure due to inadequate administrative support, poor working conditions, poor infrastructural facilities, and the burden of paper work and lack of resources are all identified as stressors to the university academics Nigeria. According to Bala (2013) the new private universities and those established by the state and federal governments had snatched most of the lecturers from other higher institutions. This condition brought about unfavourable lecturer-students ratio whereby the number of academic staff increased

by geometric progressions; it is presumed that the situation can affect the health of the academic. According to Egu, Ogbonno, Obike & Obiuto (2014), Universities academics people owing to attractive packages attached to their job. They added that academics enjoy longer service tenure (65-75 years), sabbatical leaves, and contract opportunities after retirement; light work load and other packages such as trip to overseas for study and conferences, free medical services and free education for their children at primary as well as secondary schools. Barkuzein and Rottimens (2008) observed that many of these attractions and advantages are being eroded over the past two decades and it comes as a surprise that universities are now commonly labelled as “*stress factory*.” Academic staff in universities are now subjected to stress such as meeting deadline is submitting documents, changes in methods and approaches of teaching, innovations, unbearable workloads, poor funding, lack of time, lack of control and autonomy, environmental noise, poor ventilation, lack of excessive paper-work and administrative duties and some of the challenges faced by academic staff may result to large number of health consequences. There is an excessive work-load and hours of work coupled with the dearth of teachers in the institution, the teacher-student ratio new stands at 1:500, causing most of the students had to squat on bare floor or hang on windows during lectures. These entire circumstances compound to be stressful to academics staff.

Methodology

This study was carried out to investigate leisure tourism travel as a strategy in health promotion and education in stress management and organizational commitment of academic. Staff in Ahmadu Bello University Zaria Nigeria; description survey design was used in this study because data was collected from few academic staff that represented the entire staff of ABU Zaria using Questionnaire. The population of this comprised all academic staff of thirteen faculties existing in ABU. The population of all academic staff of tertiary institutions used for this study was with a population of two thousand and thirty six (2,036). A sample of 328 academic staff the faculty of Education ABU Zaria was used for this study, proportionate sampling technique was used to select 20% of total population of academic staff from the faculties and simple random sampling technique was to select the respondents from departments.

To achieve the purpose of this study, a self-developed questionnaire was used for the study five Likert scale for each response option assigned numerical values such as: Always (5 point), Almost always (1 points). Sometime (3 points), rarely (2 point) and Never (1 point); Five copies of the questionnaire were vetted (face and content validity) by five lecturers in the Department of Physical and Health Education, ABU Zaria. To

determine the reliability of the instrument, split-half reliability method was employed using Spearman-Brown Prophecy formula. Twenty copies of the questionnaire were used for pilot study. The instrument had reliability index of 0.75. Frequency count and percentages were used to present and organize the demographic information of the respondents. Chi-Square was used to test the major hypothesis, t-test was used to test sub-hypothesis 1 and 2 and ANOVA was used to test sub-hypothesis 3 at 0.05 level Significance

Results

To determine if there is or no significant health implication of work-related stress on academic staff, Chi-Square was used and the result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Chi-square Summary on Health Implications of Work-related Stress on Academic Staff of ABU Zaria

Health implications	Observed frequency	Expected frequency	X ²	df	P-value
Positive	105	164.0	42.451	1	.001
Negative	223	164.0			
Total	328	328.0			

The result in the Table 1 showed that 105 academic staff of tertiary institutions in ABU Zaria was having positive health implications which is interpreted to be less health implications while 223 out of 328 of them were having health implications of work-related stress. The Table also, showed that P-value is less than the x value ($P=0.01 < 0.05$).

Research Question 1: *What are the health indicators of work related health stress and implications on academic staff?*

To ascertain if there is significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress on academic staff based on institutional ownership, t-test was used to test the hypothesis and the result was presented in table 2.

Table 2: t-test Summary on Difference in the Health Implications of Work-related Stress on Academic Staff based on Institutional Ownership in Zaria

Institutional Ownership value	N	Mean	Std. deviator	Std. error	t	df	P-
State tertiary institution	192	1.73	.446	.032	2.285	326	.023
Federal tertiary institution	136	1.61	.489	.042			
Total	328						

Table 4.1.3 showed that the mean value of State tertiary institution was greater than Federal owned tertiary institution ($1.73 > 1.61$). It also showed that P-value is less than level of significance ($P = 0.023 < 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress on academic staff based on institutional ownership in Zaria was rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress on academic staff based on institutional ownership in Zaria.

Research Question 2: *What are the health implications differences of work-related stress between male and female academic staff?*

The hypothesis was tested, using t-test as presented on Table 4.1.4. Table 4.1.4 revealed that male academic staff had mean value which was relatively greater than female academic staff mean value ($1.69 > 1.66$). The table also, showed that P-value is greater than level of significance ($P = 0.650 > 0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there will be no significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress between male and female academic staff of tertiary institutions in Zaria is accepted. Hence, there is no significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress between male and female academic staff of tertiary institutions in Zaria.

Research Question 3: *What is the health implications of work-related stress associated with their positions (rank) on academic staff? One-way ANOVA was used and the result was presented in Table 3.*

Table 3: Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) on Differences in the Health Implications of Work-related Stress on Academic staff of Tertiary Institutions in Zaria based on their Status

Health implications	Sum of squares	df	Mean Square	F	P-value
Between groups	6.248	2	3.124	15.587	.001
Within groups	65.139	325	.200		
Total	71.387	327			

Summary of one-way ANOVA different on the health implications of work-related on academic staff of tertiary institutions in Zaria based on status was presented on Table 4.1.5. The table showed that the p-value is less than the α value ($P=0.001<0.05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis which stated that there will be no significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress on academic staff of tertiary institutions in Zaria based on their status (rank) was rejected. Hence, there is significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress on academic staff of tertiary institutions in Zaria based on their status.

A preliminary survey on leisure and tourism activity survey was designed and conducted in order to assess the leisure and tourism activity pattern, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria. University staff ($n=45$) from 5 departments participated in the study, a quick and easy assessment of life style and leisure, tourism activity frequency and duration in university staffs. The reported survey instrument asked for lectures, supervision, examinations, thesis/project supervision; the life style activity types assessed were time spent in leisure and tourism. These activities were assessed for frequency; 1-2 days; 3-4 days and 5-7 days in a week as well as duration of activity: 1-2 hrs; 3-4 hrs and greater than 4 hrs. Each frequency and duration was assigned a score of 1, 2 and 3 for each of the possible responses. Total scores for each item assessed were computed as the sum of the frequency and duration scores. This instrument demonstrates low item to total correlations ($r<.20$), suggesting that the items assessed were not overlapping. In pilot testing leisure total score demonstrated a significant correlation ($r<.80$, $p<.05$, $n=45$). Similarly results were found for the tourism total score ($r>.60$, $p<.05$, $n=45$).

The Preliminary Data were processed using the SPSS-10.0 statistical program, the basic statistical parameters and contingency tables were calculated. The subprograms FREQUENCIES and CROSSTABS were used for the calculation. The probability of a correlation between the variables was accepted at a two-tailed 5% alpha error level.

Discussion

Leisure and tourism are activities that diverts, amuses or stimulate. It could be viewed as activity that refreshes and recreates; activity that renews one's health and spirit by enjoyment and relaxation. The therapeutic value of leisure and tourism makes it an important area of study worthy of investigation in the quest to overcome job/occupational stress. The implication is that low level participation in leisure and tourism activities not only causes deterioration in health but also causes accumulation of fats on human body. Useini (2009) reported that, increased fitness arises from active participation in leisure and tourism activities. Examples of such activities are endless and include sports, music, game, travel, reading arts and crafts, and dance. These activities and many contribute to improved functional abilities and economic growth of individual (Adeyanju, 2004).

The finding of this study showed the indicators of stress that have significant health implication on academic staff of the university such as headache, insomnia, depression and many others owing to work-related stress. The university it also congruent with the work of Claire and Lucy (2014), who studies Dark thoughts: mental illness in academia found out that academic staff battle with mental health problems, stroke and breakdown due to their job. The result also agreed with Atsua (2014), who carried out a research on consequences of occupational stress among academic staff of university of Maiduguri, Borno State, Nigeria and found out that there were reasonable health implications of job stress on academic staff of the institution such as headache (migraine), sleep disorders, back and neck pains, constant muscle tension, weight loss or gain, physical fatigue, lower immunity to colds and viruses hypertension and heart problems. These health implications on academic staff may be due to excessive workloads, poor and unhealthy working environment and conditions which academic staffs of tertiary institutions are subjected of throughout their duration in the service.

Probably Federal owned institution have more strict standards or policies, enabling working environments and conditions than State owned institutions on gender this study, revealed that there is no significant difference in the health implications of work-related stress between male and female academic staff of tertiary institutions. This result is in consistent with this result of Archibong et al. (2010), which indicated that there is no difference in the health implication of occupational stress between male and female academic staff. This also corresponded with the finding of Purvanova and Muros (2010), who studies gender differences in burnout: a meta-analysis, revealed that male and female (teaching employees) experiences equal health implications or problems of their job in higher institutions. There is significant

difference in the health implications of work-related stress on academic staff across the three categories established for this study namely: graduate assist/assistant lecturer, lecturer III-I, and senior lecturer and above. That the significant difference found among the cadres must be due high rank academic staff perhaps get a relieve from their junior ones by assigning the own works (semester courses, secretarial tasks, marking of assignment and exams' scripts, sending on inland and entering of scores) to the junior academic staff. By implication, the health of the junior academic staff will be in jeopardy than the high rank academic staff.

Finding of this study also revealed that tourism activities have significant influences on stress management. The finding is in line with the findings of Gump and Mathew (2000) which revealed that more frequent annual vacation for middle aged men at high risk for chronic heart disease are associated with a reduced risk for all because mortality and specifically mortality attributed to chronic heart disease. The Karakucuk (1999) posited any relaxing and entertainment activities of individuals and social cluster voluntarily taking at their leisure and recreational. Thus this finding corroborates with the findings of Sallis, Prochaska and Taylor (2000); Humpel, Owen and Leslie (2002); Killingsworth (2003) and Owen, Humpel and Leslie (2004) which stated that people who live in activity friendly environment are more likely to be more physically active during their leisure time.

However, with increased leisure and tourism activities campaign and the promotion of leisure time programmes in the universities, the researcher observed that most staffs are likely to enjoy high fitness level for the benefit of their health and work performance. It is evident that certain factors act as determinants of participation in leisure and tourism activities among staff of Universities. Despite the apparent health benefits of leisure and tourism participation, there is evidence that a sizeable percentage of individuals across Nigeria still fail to meet the current recommended levels of daily physical activity (Shehu, (2004). According to the 2005 Youth Risk Behaviour Survey (YRBS), a median of only 34% of the study's participants met the standard for leisure and tourism yet a median of 55% participated in one or more leisure run by the school or community (Shehu, 2007). Adesoye & Talabi (2004) revealed that as a result of academic and occupational demand in Nigerian universities, the average staff find it difficult to know what goes on in a gymnasium or relate positively to activities outside academic program.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Work-related stress has many kinds and connotes negative impressions which can affect health; job/occupational stress is a global issue at hand that poses a threat to the health of workers especially academic staff of tertiary institutes in Nigeria, these arise when workers' skill, resources and abilities cannot match with their work demands requirements. Studies have affirmed that stress accompanies work. Thus, work-related stress seem to be associated with several health problems ranging from acute to chronic health problems; cardiovascular disorders like attack to ulcers. Considerable research has been conducted in the area of physical activity, leisure and tourism, but majority of recent reports suggest that leisure and tourism as an intervention strategy progresses through a set of information stages before reaching the maintenance stage when leisure and tourism have been integrated as part of their lives activities.

The present investigation will help fill the gap in literature by expanding previous findings among academic staff and the public in regard to the associations/relationship of leisure, tourism, work stress and organizational commitment in Nigeria Universities, information concerning the most frequently health problems can be used to guide the health reforms and work policy of universities in Nigeria and as one of the ultimate health promotion and education goals is to promote leisure, and tourism activities participation as a long term healthy life style. Since this additional research may confirms the high level of interest in leisure and tourism adherence services in the current study, sports administrators may want to consider supporting the development of standardize assessment and adherence services to increase the likely hood of staff maintaining healthy active lifestyles.

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